

Ludlul Bel Nemeqi

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Ludlul bēl nēmeqi, “I will praise the lord of wisdom,” is the incipit title of a Babylonian narrative poem that recounts the divinely-imposed suffering of the poem’s protagonist, one Shubshi-meshre-Shakkan, and his divinely-effected restoration. The poem is sometimes referred to as the “Babylonian Job,” though its contents differ significantly from the biblical book. About seventy cuneiform tablets and fragments attest the poem (a number that grows every few months due to new discoveries), from which scholars have reconstructed about three-quarters of its original text. The poem likely extended to some six hundred lines in antiquity, which ancient copyists divided into five sections called “Tablets.” Modern scholars number these with Roman numerals (I–V); Arabic numerals indicate line numbers within each Tablet. The poem opens in the first-person voice of the protagonist, who praises the wrath and mercy of the Babylonian high god Marduk (I 1–40), the deity responsible for the man’s suffering and eventual recovery. In the lines immediately following the hymn the protagonist describes in a retrospective manner Marduk’s past anger toward him, which resulted in his loss of divine protectors and his reception of unfavorable signs and terrifying dreams. Expelled from his house, the protagonist recounts how he evoked the ire of his king and the jealousy of his colleagues, who schemed against him. Alienated from his community, family, and friends, the protagonist found himself completely alone; no one came to his aide. At the end of Tablet I without possessions, property, or professional position; grief-stricken, afraid, and helpless, Shubshi-meshre-Shakkan resolutely hoped for the arrival of relief. But, at the start of Tablet II, the second year of his trials, he was utterly disappointed. Surrounded by evil and without help from his personal deities and ritual experts, the protagonist tells how confused he was about his mistreatment despite his sincere piety and ritual observances. This cognitive dissonance induced doubt in him about the knowability of the gods and elicited musings on the frailty and vacillations of human life. Giving up on such lofty and troubling thoughts, the protagonist describes a litany of demonically-delivered infirmities that plagued him, the language of which resonates strongly with lamentations and lists of symptoms in medical texts. As his condition worsened, he was confined to his bed; he gained no help from ritual specialists; and he received no mercy from his gods. At the end of Tablet II, with burial preparations and mourning complete, he tells how he awaited death. In the first half of Tablet III, the protagonist describes (three or) four dreams (interpretations vary), in which several divine beings appeared to him, speaking a message of deliverance and healing. Marduk’s wrath was finally appeased; the high god had heard the man’s pleas for salvation. In a broken passage, it seems that the protagonist admits to his sins and acts of negligence. In the remainder of Tablet III, the ending of which is unrecovered, the protagonist describes the reversal of his infirmities, which continues into the very fragmentary and incompletely reconstructed Tablet IV. At the opening of Tablet V, Shubshi-meshre-Shakkan, now fully restored to health, praises Marduk, who is explicitly and emphatically referred to as the protagonist’s lord. Shubshi-meshre-Shakkan describes how after his restoration he entered the Esagil temple complex, the temple of Marduk in Babylon, to perform rituals of thanksgiving. As he entered twelve different temple gates, he received items related to his restoration (e.g., abundance, life, clear signs, release from guilt, relief of lamentation, etc.). After recounting these ritual activities at the temple, the poem leaves the protagonist’s first-person voice behind as it offers a crescendo of praise that moves from the citizens of Babylon to all of humanity. Although the conclusion to the poem, now cast in the voice of an omniscient third-person narrator, is not entirely recovered, its doxological intent is without doubt: “your (Marduk’s) praise is sweet!” (V 120). Ludlul bēl nēmeqi was a literary classic in ancient Mesopotamia. The dozens of inscribed tablets bearing the poem’s text all come from major libraries and archives in first millennium BCE cities, including Nineveh, Ashur, Kalḥu, Sippar, Babylon, and Kish. At least

fifteen of these textual witnesses are school exercise tablets, providing evidence of the poem's use in scribal training and enculturation. The poem was also the subject of an ancient commentary, which indicates an active interest in the poem in the middle of the first millennium. Moreover, a few of the poem's lines are used as explanatory citations in commentaries on other texts, including one from Hellenistic Uruk (late 4th century BCE), which attests to the poem's on-going cultural cachet. Many scholars believe the poem was composed in the last quarter of the second millennium, but there is currently no solid proof for this reasonable hypothesis. It was certainly composed sometime between the reign of Babylonian Kassite king Nazimaruttash (r. 1301-1277 BCE), who the poem mentions by name (in V 100 or V 101 [reconstructions vary]), and the copying of the earliest Neo-Assyrian textual witnesses (c. 9-8th century BCE). The author of the poem is unknown. Since, however, the poem betrays a knowledge of medical vocabulary, the incantatory and lament traditions, anti-witchcraft texts, demonology, temple ritual and geography, as well as learned scribal hermeneutics, its author was very likely a scribal scholar from the ranks of the professional exorcists.

Date Range: 1300 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Ancient Mesopotamia

Region tags: Syria, Iraq

A rough map of the ancient Near Eastern region of Mesopotamia.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Annus, Amar and Alan Lenzi. 2010. *Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi: The Standard Babylonian Poem of the Righteous Sufferer*. State Archives of Assyria Cuneiform Texts 7. Helsinki: The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project.
- Source 2: Oshima, Takayoshi. 2014. *Babylonian Poems of Pious Sufferers: Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi and the Babylonian Theodicy*. ORA 14. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck.
- Source 3: Lenzi, Alan. 2023. *Suffering in Babylon: Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi and the Scholars, Ancient and Modern*. *Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis*. Leuven: Peeters.

Notes: The printed text editions cited here (Annus and Lenzi 2010; Oshima 2014) are outdated now that the eBL has published a new edition of the poem online. But they are still worth consulting. See also the much older edition: Lambert, W. G. 1960. *Babylonian Wisdom Literature*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Reprinted, Winona Lake: Eisenbrauns, 1996. Lenzi 2023 is an interpretive monograph.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Lenzi, A., 2015, "Commentary on Ludlul (CCP 1.3)," Cuneiform Commentaries Project (E. Frahm, E. Jiménez, M. Frazer, and K. Wagensonner), 2013–2023; accessed March 7, 2023, at <https://ccp.yale.edu/P394923>. DOI: 10079/cc2frb2
- Source 1 Description: Text edition of the ancient scribal commentary on the text of Ludlul.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.ebl.lmu.de/corpus/L/2/2>

– Source 1 Description: Aino Häätinen. Text Edition of the Righteous Sufferer (Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi). Electronic Babylonian Literature Project. 2023.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

– Other [specify]: Reed stylus on wet clay.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

Clay object

– Clay tablet

Type of clay

– Type of clay: Varies by location.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No
- ↳ Temple
 - Yes
- ↳ Shrine
 - Yes
- ↳ Altar
 - No
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - I don't know
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Notes: The tablets were found in a variety of ancient sites, palatial and domestic. In Neo-Assyrian palatial and temple archival/library contexts, there would have been iconography incised on the walls of nearby rooms.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: In some contexts in which the poem was copied, there would have been royal patronage. In other contexts, the copyist may simply have been doing scribal homework or

copying a tablet as another scribe's junior apprentice.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Notes: This question is not easily answered due to the nature of the ancient society, which lacked a clear distinction between polity and religious leaders.

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some interpretations of Ludlul suggest the scribe(s) who composed the poem intended to shape politico-religious practices.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, the scribes responsible for the copying and curating of the poem may have been "full time," in that they worked as scribal-scholars in the royal court.

↳ Present part-time?

– Yes

Notes: Some scribes likely copied the poem to have a copy of it in their own collection or so another scribe would have a copy of it in their collection.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– Yes

Notes: The scribal-scholars who likely composed the poem and the later ones who transmitted it were all men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– Yes

Notes: The poem's Babylonian deity and the locales mentioned in the poem suggest a Babylonian origin of the poem. The transmission of the poem occurred among both Babylonian and Assyrian scribal-scholars, their students, as well as Babylonian and Assyrian palatial and temple archives/libraries.

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– Yes

↳ Is this class/caste based on a cultural status?

– Yes

Notes: Due to the nature of advanced scribal literacy, scribes who could copy and curate this poem would have been considered educated and cultured, a distinct advantage that did not guarantee economic prosperity but would have provided the means for it.

↳ Is this class/caste based on socioeconomic status?

– Yes

Notes: To become a scribal scholar, one would have needed extensive household support. The household would have had to have been wealthy enough to forego the labor of one of its members during his scribal training.

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

Notes: Scribes often stayed in one city during their careers, but there are examples of scribes moving from one place to another.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?

– Yes

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: There weren't schools per se; rather, most scribes learned the craft from a senior scribe in a domestic setting.

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– Yes

Notes: The institutional element varies across the first millennium BCE. Some contexts are palatial-centered, others may have the temple as a focal point.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Standard Babylonian Akkadian is a literary dialect that likely would have sounded archaic to many first millennium speakers of the language. And by the middle of the first millennium, many in society would have spoken a form of Aramaic.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: However, some interpreters suggest the poem intended to make a religio-ritual and/or theological statement about Marduk's position in the pantheon and his proper cultic veneration.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text is remarkably similar across witnesses attesting the text over several centuries, but there are minor variations. Might these reflect distinct versions? It doesn't seem likely, but the matter is not entirely settled.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The poem is clearly associated with the scribal curricula of the first millennium. It was copied at an advanced stage of scribal training. Was the text considered a part of something else beyond this? Likely. The text was a literary classic and thus formed the "internal library" of educated people.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We don't know exactly why the text was composed, though some think it was simply a thanksgiving hymn for an individual. What is clear is that the poem became something of a classic, used in scribal training and kept in royal and temple libraries/archives.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text is a narrative poem that draws heavily on ritual language and technical vocabulary.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: The poem describes the grave as a kind of pit from which the protagonist is pulled up (see the opening lines of Tablet V).

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Funerary preparations are stated as happening but not described.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– I don't know

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– Yes

↳ Personal effects?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Valuable/precious items?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See II 114. The text is quite vague.

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions a grave but does not specify its location. Ancient Mesopotamians sometimes buried their dead below the floor of a house. The poem is unclear about the location of the protagonist's grave.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: Mourning (see II 115)

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: Marduk is the high god of the pantheon.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Marduk is praised for his anger, which eventually (typically) gives way to his mercy.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: Only indirectly.

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Notes: Religious specialists are the norm. But the high god can use dreams to communicate, although in the dreams in this poem human ritual specialists appear as his messengers/agents.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: A few ritual specialists appear in a series of dreams in Tablet III. I consider these "human spirits" for the present purpose.

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– No

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– No

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– No

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

Notes: They seem to understand the protagonist's suffering, empathize with him, and deliver a message of hope and healing.

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

Notes: They know that the protagonist is going to recover.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
–Specify: Effective ritual knowledge.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: See the series of dreams in Tablet III.

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

- ↳ Only through monarch
- No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: Demons: no. Personal deities, perhaps if they are among those who appear in the dreams of Tablet III.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Yes

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - No
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - Notes: There are demons in the text and there are personal deities of the protagonist mentioned in the text.
- ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Demons "communicate" in that they can make a person ill and experience social problems.
- ↳ In dreams?
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession?
 - No
- ↳ Through divination practices?
 - No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Personal deities/protective spirits do, yes. Demons do not, typically.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Demons do not. But personal deities/protective spirits accept offerings of victuals.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Demons are anthropomorphized but lack other humanizing elements.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Typically. However, Marduk as presented in Ludlul is all-powerful.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The alû-demon has severe physical effects on the protagonist in II 71-84.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

Notes: The protagonist states that he cannot see the alû-demon.

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: "Hidden" may be too strong. The alû-demon is not visible, apparently by its very nature.

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Notes: Marduk's divine mind is said to be incomprehensible even to other deities (see I 33-36).

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

Notes: If ritual adherence is pro-social, which I think it was, then yes.

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?
– Yes

↳ Daily life objects?
– Yes

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Notes: Not in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: "Place" is unclear.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Deliberate abandonment of personal deities/protective spirits leaves the protagonist unprotected against various demonic attacks.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Sin is the root of divine anger, which brings punishment in the form of social ostracization and physical infirmity.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

Notes: Not described in this text. But in ancient Mesopotamia: Yes.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Ultimately, yes, though he uses agents.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– No
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: I think this is highly interpretive. I have only indicated the ones that seem clearly evidenced in the text or clearly not relevant to the text.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the protagonist asserts that he teaches the people to fear the gods and king.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the protagonist asserts that he teaches the people to fear the gods and king.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the protagonist bemoans his social alienation from his household.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the protagonist bemoans the alienation from those over whom he has authority (e.g., his servants).

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the protagonist must rely on ritual specialists to help him understand his plight. They fail.

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the poem suggests one need only wait Marduk's anger out. He will become merciful in due course.

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that the poem suggests one need only wait Marduk's anger out. He will become merciful in due course.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Notes: One should be confident in Marduk's power and his mercy.

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: The text shows a very clearly patriarchal hierarchy in the society depicted.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: The poem advocates for its readers to trust in Marduk's divine plan. He may be angry for the moment but he also shows mercy in the end.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: There is enthusiasm in the praise of Marduk.

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: The poem advocates for its readers to trust in Marduk's divine plan. He may be angry for the moment but he also shows mercy in the end.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: One of the things the poem does is to give thanksgiving praise for Marduk's deliverance of the protagonist, who is a kind of paradigm for others who may be suffering.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Marduk possesses wisdom and understanding; and the poem purports to pass a kind of wisdom along to its readers.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: Marduk possesses discernment and intelligence; and the poem purports to pass a kind of wisdom along to its readers.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: In that two figures who appear in the dreams are said to be attractive or extraordinary in terms of their appearance.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Proper ritual observances will take time.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Yes

Notes: One should do the rituals correctly. But no one is going around policing people.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?
– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?
– Yes

↳ Comedy?
– No

↳ Tragedy?
– Yes

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Descriptively, not prescriptively. But, what is described might have been what was consider necessary or required.

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– I don't know

Notes: The ritual activity is voluntary. But are the specific items offered---when elected to be offered---mandatory, I don't know.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– No

Notes: The rituals seem to be voluntary in the text, done in thanksgiving after the protagonist's recovery.

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: We don't know exactly when the poem was composed. It was likely composed in post-Kassite Babylonia, which had a monarchy. Beyond that, I'm not sure how we would want to label its political organization in the above terms.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Scribal scholars in a loose professional association, of sorts.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– Yes

Notes: The protagonist mentions teaching others to revere the gods.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Notes: However, the text was used in the training of scribes, some of whom would go on to work in palace/temple contexts.

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

Notes: The protagonist is described as walking along a particular street in Babylon. Also, he goes to some temples, which I think can be considered public works.

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– No

↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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